

THE CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *VATERIA INDICA*, PART II. THE COMPONENT GLYCERIDES OF THE FAT

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The component glycerides of *Vateria indica* fat work out to be tri-stearin (2.5%), oleo-distearin (44.9%), oleo-palmitostearin (16.6%), oleo-dipalmitin (7.1%), dioleo-stearin (15.8%), dioleo-palmitin (13.0%) and triolein (0.2%).

The detailed examination of solid seed fats is at present of general theoretical as well as of practical importance. Theoretically there are two reasons: (i) to collect sufficient data to establish ultimately the limits within which specific mixture of fatty acids in seed fats is characteristic of particular botanical family and (ii) to obtain further evidence about their glyceride structure and about the even distribution of fatty acids throughout the whole glyceride molecule (Collin and Hilditch, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 1273). The practical importance in the study of the glyceride structure of solid seed fats centres round their applicability in confectionery and soap industry in comparison with other favoured natural fats like Cacao butter, Borneo tallow and Kokum butter and hydrogenated fats. The physical properties namely the brittleness or 'snap' and low m.p. common to the above fats might be due to some similarities in glyceride structure.

The glyceride structure of the fat from *Vateria indica* was not investigated previously. The only other member of the family *Dipterocarpaceae*, which was completely studied with regard to its fatty acids and glyceride structure, is Borneo-tallow (Hilditch and Priestman, *J. Soc., Chem. Ind.*, 1930, 49, 1977). A comparison of these fats with other solid seed fats is made at the end of this article. The glyceride composition was determined by methods recently adopted by a number of investigators (Amberger and Bauch, *Z. Unters. Nahr. Genussen.*, 1924, 46, 371; Hilditch and Lea, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 3106; Lewkowitsch., *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1933, 82, 236 7; Hilditch and Ichaporia., *ibid.*, 1938, 87, 44).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Fully Saturated Glyceride.—100 G. of neutral fat (free acidity being removed by treating with excess of sodium carbonate solution) were oxidised repeatedly with powdered potassium permanganate in acetone medium according to Hilditch and Lea (*loc. cit.*), when 2.5 g. of neutral matter were obtained which contained 0.1 g. of non-saponifiable matter. The neutral substance on crystallising from ether gave pure tri-stearin, m.p. 71° (S.E. 294.7; I.V. 1.2). Hence the fat contains 2.4% of saturated glycerides mainly consisting of tri-stearin.

Separation of the Glycerides from Acetone.—300 G. of neutral fat were systematically crystallised from acetone at 0°. The least soluble glycerides (A) and soluble glycerides (B) were separated and the corresponding acids were liberated. These acids were esterified separately and subjected to fractional distillation.

* TABLE I

	(A)	(B)	Neutral fat.
Wt. in g.	198	102	300
S.E.	295.5	290.2	293.8
I.V.	28.5	51.1	36.1
Glyceride by wt. %	66	34	100
Glyceride by mol. %	65.6	34.4	100

** TABLE II

	Composition of acids by wt. %			Composition by mol. %		
	(A)	(B)	Mean	(A)	(B)	Mean
Palmitic	77.98	25.36	13.7	8.56	27.27	14.97
Stearic	59.98	13.56	43.5	58.36	13.14	42.85
Oleic	33.18	61.58	42.5	33.07	59.61	41.17

* The percentage of fatty acids in each portion was determined in the usual way by identifying individual acids and calculating their proportions from the fractions.

** Myristic acid is taken together with palmitic acid and arachidic acid with stearic acid. Oleic acid contains traces of linoleic acid.

In order to find out the quantity of tri-C₁₈ glycerides in the fat, fractions (A) and (B) were fully hydrogenated with suspended nickel as catalyst until the iodine values were nearly nil: 1.2 and 2.1. The hydrogenated fat was systematically crystallised from ether at 0° when almost quantitative separation of tri-stearin was effected, 48.6% from (A) and 13.8% from (B) were obtained.

TABLE III

Fractionation of the esters of solid acids at 2 mm. pressure

Fr. No.	Temp. of fraction.	Weight.	S.E.	I.V.
1	82-141°	7.2 g.	291.4	3.2
2	141°	13.1	293.8	2.8
3	141°-145°	9.7	295.3	2.6
4	145°-152°	16.5	296.1	1.9
5	152°-154°	8.4	299.2	2.1
Residue	—	11.6	300.2	1.9

From the above observations the glyceride composition of the fat is calculated and given in Table IV below.

TABLE IV

Mol % of the fatty acids

	(A)	(B)	Total.
Mol %	65.6	34.4	100
Palmitic	5.6	9.4	15.0
Stearic	38.3	4.5	42.8
Oleic	21.7	20.5	42.2

Component glycerides (mol %)

Tri-C ₁₈ glycerides	48.6	13.8	62.4
(a) Fully saturated glycerides (tri-stearin)	2.4	—	2.4
(b) Mono-oleo-disaturated glycerides			
Oleo-distearin	44.1	—	44.1
Oleo-palmitostearin	16.8	—	16.8
Oleo-dipalmitin	—	7.5	7.5
(c) Dioleo-mono-saturated glycerides			
Dioleo-stearin	2.1	13.5	15.6
Dioleo-palmitin	—	13.2	13.2
(d) Tri-unsaturated glycerides			
Triolein	—	0.2	0.2

The following facts were taken into consideration in calculating the above proportions:

Fraction A.—The fully saturated glycerides, tristearin and oleo-distearin will remain in this fraction as they are most insoluble in acetone at 0°. Most of the oleo-palmitostearin being sparingly soluble in acetone at 0° will also be with this fraction.

Fraction B.—This fraction will consist mainly of di-unsaturated glycerides with small quantities of di-saturated glycerides. The whole of the tri-unsaturated glycerides will be found in this fraction only. But in the case of this fat no evidence has been found for its presence.

The fat from *Vateria indica* contains 2.5% of tri-stearin, 44.9% oleo-distearin, 16.6% oleo-palmitostearin, 15.8% dioleo-stearin; 13.0% dioleo-palmitin, 7.1% oleo-dipalmitin and 0.2% triolein.

	Myristic %.	Palmitic %.	Stearic %.	Arachidic %.	Oleic %.	Linoleic %.	Association ratio in the total fatty acids.
<i>Vateria indica</i>	0.7	13.0	43.1	0.4	42.5	0.1	1.34
Borneo-tallow	1.5	21.5	39.0	—	38.0	—	1.63
M. p.		<i>Vateria indica</i> 35-37*		Borneo-tallow* 33-37**		Cacao butter† 32-34†	Kokum butter‡ 37-39*
Assn. ratio		1.3		1.6		1.4	1.4
Glycerides (in round figures)							
Tri-stearin		2.5		5		2	2
Oleo-distearin		45		40		19	59
Oleo-palmitostearin		16.5		31		52	14
Oleo-dipalmitin		7		8		6	2
Stearo-diolein		16		13		12	21
Palmito-diolein		13		3		9	2
Triolein		—		—		—	1

The fat from *Vateria indica* adds to the list of solid seed fats which follow the even distribution of fatty acids having association ratio on the total fatty acids 1.3 to 1.6.

The glyceride structure of the fat shows more similarities with that of Borneo-tallow.

It should find more favourable place in confectionery due to its pleasant smell and can be industrially utilised for soap-making and as a source of stearic acid.

* Bushell and Hilditch, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1918, 57, 447.

† Collin, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, 48, 41 r.

‡ Vidyarthi and Dasa Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 437.